

Quark Visualization – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the framework alongside the coupling constants primordial series, it is than possible to construct a visual model of the idea of quarks. In the 8-theory framework, quarks are regarded to be an arbitrary amount of curvature on the manifold. The manifold a Lorentz manifold with (3,1) signature, which is invoked stationary, $M = M_0 \times R$ by Lagrangian operator.

Introduction

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.13)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} = 0 \quad (1.14)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M(1)} \frac{\partial M(1)}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} \frac{\partial s(n)}{\partial M(n)} \frac{\partial M(n)}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.15)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0$$

δg As amount of arbitrary variations, which by demands of stationarity we require to vanish. Discretizing and partitioning the term δg into a series of sub elements, we can derive the existence of fermions, i.e. showing that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$$

In the 8 theory thesis we proved such a series must contain an even amount of elements which differ in sign. By allowing to the sub elements to vary as well, given only two elements in the series, there is a creating of threefold combinations .Let it be only four elements in the series and one of the pluses just changed its nature:

$$0: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 \neq 0$$

There must be a way to bring it back to where it was, so the overall series can vanish, it takes another map, on the varying element to bring it back to where it was.

$$Y: \delta g_2 \rightarrow \delta g_1$$

Therefore, to bring an element to itself given only two varying elements in the series we need two distinct maps, which attach a varying element to itself, by a threefold combination.

$$\delta g_1(0)\delta g_2(Y)\delta g_1$$

that is the thesis construction of quarks. That is how we derived the coupling constants primorial function, using three critical theorems and regarding bosonic fields as net curvature on the manifold. How does a threefold combination of quark is presented visually? That is of course harder to create, but as Dirac once said: "one must try".

Imagine constant variation so the overall construction is curvature varying, according to the combination where will be a pairing according the graph presented in the 8 theory thesis or the group suggested by the particle physicist Gell Mann. Each arrow in the visual is a representation of the gluon, or the first element in the coupling constant primorial function.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.16}$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{v=1}^{V=R} N_v + (3) \right) + N_v = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.17}$$

$$N_v = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.18}$$

$$N_v \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_v = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.19}$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)